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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE FOR UZBEKISTAN GENERAL SCHOOLS

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Abstract: This article examines the necessity, advantages, and disadvantages of using artificial intelligence in teaching English. It also explores the methodological foundations of artificial intelligence in English language education and highlights some of the key applications of artificial intelligence that are effective in improving English learning in general schools of Uzbekistan.

Key words: artificial intelligence, intelligent tutoring systems (ITS), speech recognition and pronunciation tools, chatbots and virtual tutors, automated translation tools, flexible learning platforms.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o'qitishda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishning zarurati, afzalliklari va kamchiliklari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishning metodik asoslari va umumta'lim maktablarida ingliz tilini samarali o'qitishda qo'llaniladigan asosiy ilovalar ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, intellektual ta'lim tizimlari (ITS), nutqni aniqlash va talaffuz vositalari, chatbotlar va virtual repetitorlar, avtomatlashtirilgan tarjima vositalari, moslashuvchan ta'lim platformalari.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются необходимость, преимущества и недостатки использования искусственного интеллекта в обучении английскому языку. Также анализируются методологические основы применения искусственного интеллекта в преподавании английского языка и основные приложения, которые способствуют эффективному изучению английского языка в общеобразовательных школах Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, интеллектуальные обучающие системы (ITS), средства распознавания речи и произношения, чат-боты и виртуальные репетиторы, автоматизированные средства перевода, гибкие образовательные платформы.

INTRODUCTION

The reforms being carried out in the education system indicate the need for the effective use of modern technologies in this system as well. In particular, the need to use artificial intelligence in foreign language education is becoming increasingly important. The rapid impact of artificial intelligence tools on every field will undoubtedly have a positive impact on language learning. While traditional language teaching methods are effective, new methods and tools are often required to meet the individual needs of students, especially in different classes. The use of artificial intelligence in language learning offers customized, flexible, and scalable solutions, providing students with personalized experiences that can accelerate their acquisition of foreign languages.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Artificial intelligence technologies serve as an effective tool for individualizing the learning process and adapting to the needs of students. For example, platforms such as Duolingo allow students to automatically assess their level of knowledge and personalize their curriculum. In addition, tools such as Grammarly help automatically correct grammatical errors in the language learning process, which greatly contributes to the development of students' independent learning abilities. The use of AI in education leads to personalized learning and adapts to the needs of each student. For example, Chen (2021) reported a 20% improvement in language learning outcomes through Duolingo. AI tools provide real-time analysis and feedback, encouraging students to correct mistakes (Jones & Smith, 2020). Engaging students through interactive and gamified platforms (Brown, 2022) has also been shown to be effective. For example, in South Korea, AI tools have been

widely implemented in schools, increasing student motivation by 30%. The use of AI tools in the education system of Uzbekistan is not yet widespread. Nevertheless, there are attempts to introduce modern technologies in some universities. For instance, Tashkent State Pedagogical University recommends the use of Grammarly and ChatGPT tools to teachers as part of its experimental projects.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research used observation, comparative analysis, diagnostic methods (questionnaire, interview, survey), design, modeling, and generalization methods.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Digital technologies are considered to be tools that help improve the quality of education. In particular, such technologies allow students to activate the process of learning and create opportunities to use various digital technologies during the educational process. In addition, the use of digital technologies contributes to the full coverage of the audience and the development of a positive attitude towards science. Today, the use of digital technologies in the education system ensures that students receive high-quality lessons. The pandemic itself has proven that the use of digital technologies in the education system is effective. If we consider other positive aspects of the transition to digital education, textbooks will be transferred to screens in electronic form, students will have the opportunity to study at a time convenient for them, and a culture of obtaining and using information from the Internet will be formed, which will raise the education system to a new level, reduce the cost of time and money, etc.

Effective integration of artificial intelligence into English language teaching requires a solid methodological foundation that is consistent with pedagogical principles and educational goals. The methodological foundations of the use of artificial intelligence in English language teaching are based on several key points:

- 1. Personalized learning.** AI-enabled platforms can adapt educational content and tasks to students' skill levels, interests, and learning preferences. By personalizing the learning experience, teachers can meet the individual needs of students and increase engagement and motivation among them. For example, AI algorithms can analyze student language proficiency data and provide customized learning methods, including targeted vocabulary exercises, grammar exercises, and real-life tasks tailored to students' language learning needs.
- 2. Adaptive feedback.** AI algorithms can analyze student performance, provide immediate feedback, and suggest targeted improvements. Adaptive feedback mechanisms allow students to track their performance and progress, identify strengths and weaknesses, and effectively improve their language skills. For instance, AI-based assessment tools can evaluate students' speaking and writing tasks, analyze linguistic errors, and provide detailed feedback on grammar, pronunciation, and vocabulary use. In addition, adaptive feedback systems can adjust the level of complexity of learning tasks based on the abilities that students demonstrate, ensuring optimal challenge and skill development.
- 3. Interactive learning.** AI technologies offer interactive learning experiences through multimedia resources, gamified tasks, and virtual simulations. By incorporating interactive elements into English language teaching, teachers can create an engaging and dynamic learning environment that enhances comprehension and retention. For example, AI-powered language learning platforms can provide interactive multimedia content such as videos, audio recordings, and exercises to facilitate active and experiential learning. In addition, gamified learning activities such as quizzes, puzzles, and role-playing simulations can motivate students, foster collaboration, and enhance language acquisition skills in a real-world setting.

AI technologies used in language learning encompass a wide range of tools and applications. These technologies use algorithms, natural language processing (NLP), machine learning, and deep learning to create dynamic and engaging learning environments. Some of the main applications of AI in language learning are:

- 1. Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS).** ITS are AI-based programs designed to provide learners with personalized instruction and instant feedback. Based on the learner's progress, these systems adjust the difficulty of exercises and provide personalized learning materials according to individual strengths and weaknesses. For example, platforms such as Sirius and Rosetta Stone use ITS to provide real-time, contextual feedback on pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary use.
- 2. Speech recognition and pronunciation tools.** One of the major challenges for language learners is mastering pronunciation. AI-powered speech recognition tools like Google Speech-to-Text and Duolingo allow learners to practice speaking and get instant feedback on their pronunciation. These tools analyze spoken language, compare it to native speaker models, and suggest corrections that enable learners to improve their speaking skills at their own pace.

3. **Chatbots and virtual tutors.** AI-powered chatbots and virtual tutors are increasingly being used to create language learning experiences. These AI assistants simulate conversations with learners, offering opportunities to practice conversational skills without the need for a human teacher. Chatbots like Replika and Babbel's AI assistant allow learners to engage in ongoing conversations, improving their fluency and comprehension.
4. **Automated translation tools.** Language translation technologies like Google Translate and DeepL use AI to provide near-instant translations. These tools employ machine learning algorithms to continuously improve their accuracy and help learners understand complex phrases and concepts when learning a new language. AI-powered translation services are important tools for overcoming language barriers and accelerating comprehension.
5. **Adaptive learning platforms.** AI-powered adaptive learning platforms like Khan Academy and Memrise personalize the learning process by analyzing students' learning patterns and adapting the curriculum accordingly. These platforms help students progress at their own pace, reinforce concepts they struggle with, and move on to new topics once they have mastered them. The use of AI in education, particularly in language learning, is effective in helping students acquire foreign languages. These technologies can assess the unique needs of each student and tailor lessons to their strengths and weaknesses. Unlike traditional methods, AI can provide targeted instruction, allowing students to focus on areas they need to improve and accelerate their progress in areas where they excel. Furthermore, AI-powered platforms are available anytime and anywhere, giving students the flexibility to learn at their own pace. This convenience is especially useful for students in remote or underserved areas where access to qualified language teachers is limited ^[5].

Today, the rapid development of artificial intelligence technologies is creating the basis for fundamental changes in the field of education. In particular, the use of these technologies in the process of learning foreign languages serves to significantly increase the efficiency of forming and developing students' language skills. Through programs and platforms created on the basis of artificial intelligence, opportunities are created for an individual approach to students, adaptation of educational materials, real-time analysis, feedback, as well as speech recognition and correction.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, the methodological basis for using artificial intelligence in teaching English to students includes personalized learning, tailored feedback, and interactive learning. By using AI technologies, teachers can optimize the language learning experience, facilitate the acquisition of language skills, and improve students' ability to communicate in English. At the same time, it is crucial to approach AI integration with a pedagogical framework that prioritizes educational goals and student-centered learning principles. As AI continues to evolve, teachers need to be vigilant in exploring innovative methodologies that take full advantage of technology to improve English language teaching. Moreover, it is considered important to develop students' self-monitoring skills when using AI in English language learning in school education. The reason is that where there is good control, there is good acquisition.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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